

"PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS FOR FORMING MOTIVATION FOR SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH ACTIVITIES AMONG STUDENTS OF PEDAGOGICAL UNIVERSITY"**Kulsharipova Z.,***Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences (associate professor)
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Higher School of Pedagogy,
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The article discusses issues related to the problem of motivating students of pedagogical universities for scientific research activities. The problem of declining interest in science among students is justified by the need to uncover the internal reserves of the student's personality, namely - their motivation.

The modern stage of societal development has somewhat exacerbated the problem of professional training of specialists, methods of acquiring new knowledge, and the development of fundamentally new solutions to posed tasks. The research results provide scientifically based recommendations for utilizing students' research skills and creating conditions for engaging students in active scientific research, which contributes to a deeper assimilation of independent, creative, and active activities aimed at continuous updating and enriching their scientific knowledge base.

Keywords: motivation; scientific research activities; cognitive learning models; professional culture; socialization.

One of the pressing issues of modern society is the problem of pedagogical conditions for fostering motivation for scientific research activities among students of pedagogical universities, as contemporary education gives rise to numerous contradictions in the formation of motivation for scientific research activities [1]. The intensive development of international contacts, processes of globalization and integration into the global educational community significantly influence the system of higher education in Kazakhstan. The changes are aimed at creating a unified educational space with the goal of preparing specialists capable of active creative activity, self-realization, and independence, and competitiveness, social and professional mobility. The dynamics of demand for qualified personnel in the Republic of Kazakhstan contradict the established system of their training.

The relevance of the study is dictated by changes in the system of higher professional education. The transition to a competency-based approach, the introduction of multi-level programs of higher professional education provides an opportunity to abandon the traditional cognitive learning model, where students are mainly prepared for reproductive reproduction of information. The orientation of the process of professional training at the university towards the formation of professional competence in unity with the system of value orientations implies fundamentally new approaches to students' research activities at the university.

Research activity at the university is an important component of professional training, it is a multi-level

process in the context of lifelong learning, built on an interdisciplinary basis, and involves the formation of a well-rounded intellectually developed individual with high general and professional culture.

The issues of interaction in scientific research activities of university students open up new opportunities for studying aspects of motivation formation in this process, which reveal the views of scientific practitioners from different fields of science and various approaches to defining the essence of motivation for scientific research activities among students of pedagogical universities [2].

The transition to a competency-based approach is also dictated by changes in the system of higher pedagogical education, the introduction of multi-level programs of higher professional education, which allows abandoning the traditional cognitive learning model, where students are mainly prepared for reproductive reproduction of information.

The orientation of the process of professional training at the university towards the formation of professional competence in unity with the system of value orientations implies fundamentally new approaches to students' research activities at the university. Research activity at the university is an important component of professional training, it is a multi-level process in the context of lifelong learning, built on an interdisciplinary basis, and involves the formation of a well-rounded intellectually developed individual with high general and professional culture.

In today's conditions of modern information society and constant knowledge updates, the ability to quickly orient oneself in the flow of information, analyze it, extract relevant data, conduct independent research, and demonstrate its effectiveness in practice are professionally important competencies. The key role of research work in developing students' professional competencies is reflected in the educational programs of pedagogical universities across many fields of study [3].

The transition to a competency-based approach, the introduction of multi-level programs in pedagogical universities, provide an opportunity to move away from the traditional cognitive learning model, where students are mainly prepared for knowledge reproduction. The formation of professional competence of future specialists is driven by the urgency of social, cultural, and economic scientific problems in the world. Modern higher education aims to find acceptable ways to prepare competent professionals with scientific thinking, possessing comprehensive knowledge, and ready to independently solve professional tasks.

In the context of education in pedagogical universities, the implementation of a competency-based approach becomes a factor in merging with the global educational and scientific space of research and educational disciplines.

In contemporary student society, there is social instability in scientific research activities [4].

An extensive research base on the issue of forming motivation for scientific research activities among students will scientifically justify the development of strategic pedagogical conditions for solving research tasks, among which scientific-informational and socio-professional competencies are highlighted as the basis for successful scientific research activities.

Thus, the pedagogical conditions for forming motivation for scientific research activities among students cover various aspects of the scientific community and inevitably reflect on the level of research indicators. At present, one of the central scientific categories undergoing comprehensive and deep investigation is the issue of motivation for scientific research activities. The most important aspect in terms of the influence of motivation on personality and research behaviour is the process of learning. It is during this period of professional education that the system of relationships with the scientific-student environment undergoes a complete restructuring, which increases the role of research-based learning, referred to as generative didactics. Generative didactics considers the method, the research environment, knowledge, and cognition from the perspective of the learning process and the scientific development of personal thinking, as well as the way of technologizing knowledge (i.e., transforming knowledge into scientific and social objects and technologies).

Various domestic and foreign scholars have addressed issues of research-oriented socialization of young scientists, who are being shaped in the modern student community towards a changing paradigm that demands exploratory modes of thinking [5].

And the task of education as one of the institutions

of such socialization actualizes the spiritual-value logic of the development of a scientific-creative personality. Special research environments and teaching methods, through which only such a personality can be nurtured, self-revealing its individuality in the context of social relations in scientific research activities. (G. M. Andreeva, S. L. Belicheva, L. I. Bozhovich, P. P. Blonsky, L. S. Vygotsky, E. I. Kirshbaum, T. V. Dragunova, I. S. Kon, X. Remschmidt, K. N. Polivanova, D. I. Feldshtein, Z. Freud, E. Erikson, D. B. Elkonin, etc.). Various approaches to the content of motivation are reflected in the works of these authors. However, it is widely recognized that the resolution or non-resolution of pedagogical conditions has a fundamental influence on the formation of motivation for scientific research activities in the process of its socialization into future profession (V. S. Mukhina, E. S. Romanova, V. I. Slobodchikov, R. Selman, X. Remschmidt, S. Hall, R. Havighurst, etc.).

The subject of the development of future specialists is the worldview, which functions as the most essential and actively operating aspects of societal or individual consciousness that, in interaction with the social conditions of life, serve as the most significant subjective factor, internal motive for engaging in scientific research activities [6,7].

It is in the university that the formation of students' basic qualities occurs, shaping their worldview, beliefs, and attitudes towards the scientific world (A. N. Ganicheva, O. L. Zvereva, A. G. Selevko, G. K. Selevko, I. S. Kon, L. B. Schneider, etc.).

Given the significance of the university education period, it can be argued that the development of scientific worldview as a phenomenon and process of spiritual life in young people is a crucial task for the scientific community. Scientific worldview is linked to determining the objective reality of its subject and establishing possible boundaries for the practical and theoretical utilization of academic knowledge, based on actual scientific needs, determined by historical theory or the social experience of the future professional.

Overall, an analysis of the scientific literature on the issue indicates that the psychological content of emotional, cognitive, and behavioral educational interactions and their influence on the behavior of learners is insufficiently studied, resulting in a number of contradictions between the practical necessity of purposefully forming skills of conflict-free behavior in interactions and the absence of a psychological-pedagogical program to implement this goal. The need to resolve this contradiction has led to the formulation of the research problem: the scientific justification and development of an effective program for forming skills of conflict-free interaction among university students.

In this regard, the issues of studying the experience of organizing theoretical-methodological aspects and developing unique methods for forming motivation for scientific research activities among university students are relevant.

Overall, the analysis of the problem indicates that the pedagogical conditions for interaction in the practice of scientific research activities, their influence on

the motivation of future teacher-psychologists, are insufficiently studied, resulting in a number of contradictions between the practical necessity of purposefully forming scientific research activities in interactions in the scientific-student and educational environment and the absence of a psychological-pedagogical program to implement this goal.

The necessity to resolve this contradiction has led to the formulation of the research problem:

- the scientific substantiation and development of an effective program for fostering motivation for scientific research activities in the university setting;
- identifying the current state of students' scientific research work: the degree of meaningfulness of scientific preparation of pedagogical university students at the present stage;
- the extent and nature of student involvement in scientific research activities;
- the presence of organizational problems and difficulties;
- the need for the development of a corresponding program for fostering motivation for scientific research activities in the higher pedagogical education system.

In analyzing the activities of the scientific circle, we studied the main directions of students' motivation for scientific research activities. As a result of the conducted scientific sections, the most active students were given the opportunity to participate;

- in the International Scientific-Practical Online Conference "Psychology, Pedagogy, and Social Work: Theory and Practice of Interaction" on November 11, 2023. (Anastasiya Sergeevna Girich; Marzhan Yermagambetkyzy Kusain);
- in the International Scientific Research Competition "Science without Borders" with the receipt of 1st-degree diplomas (Kairkhan Tuyakpayuly Abdulman; Adel Ruslanovna Bekenova; Rakhimzhan Galymzhanovich Ergaliev; Victoria Aleksandrovna Shandanovina).
- in the International Online Psychology Olympiad "Introduction to Psychology" for students, with the awarding of 1st place diplomas (Gulnara Zinelgabilovna Kurenbaeva, Moldir Talgatovna Temirgaukova, Aisulu Askhatovna Kasymova, Albina Urazgalinova, Aruzhan Yestaevna Alzhanova).

To assess the effectiveness of motivational opportunities during the training stage on the topic of "Career Growth and Tutoring Support," a survey was con-

ducted. Quantitative indicators were recorded in percentages, while qualitative ones were assessed using judgments such as "high," "medium," "low."

Using the Fisher criterion, it was established that before the experiment, the statistical groups were almost indistinguishable. To confirm this fact, students in the experimental and control groups were asked to complete special creative tasks in the form of essays.

The assessment could range from 100% - indicating the optimal level of knowledge, skills, and abilities, to 0% - indicating a complete absence of knowledge, skills, and abilities. Based on the adopted criteria and their indicators, three levels of cognitive motivation were identified: low, medium, and high. All digital indicators of research work are presented in the study. Thus, based on the research results, the conclusion becomes evident that future young specialists lack skills in research and development work.

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